

D7.1

Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication Activities

```
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timeout={500}  
classNames="menu-secondary"  
unmountOnExit  
onEnter={calcHeight}  
>  
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<h4>Kemball</h4>  
</DropdownItem>  
  
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  return (  
    <DropdownItem  
      leftIcon={<BoltIcon />}  
      goToMenu={linkName}  
      goHref={vallink.link}  
    >  
      {vallink.name}  
    </DropdownItem>  
  )  
})  
</div>  
</CSSTransition>  
</div>
```

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.App {  
  text-align: center;  
}
```


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D7.1	Work Package No.	WP7	Task/s No.	Task 7.1
Work Package Title	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation			
Linked Task/s Title	Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication			
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)		
Dissemination level	PU-Public	Grant Agreement Nº 101103667		
Due date deliverable	31/08/2023	Submission date	28/09/2023	
Deliverable version	Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication Activities			

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Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.1	2023-08-18	Initial version
1.2.	2023-09-28	Final version with the revision and comments from partners.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
RP	Reporting Period
TC	Technical Committee
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work Package
R&D	Research and Development
OBJ	Objectives
DT	Digital twin

SPECIFIC ACRONYMS	
A3C: Asynchronous Actor-Critic Agent	KPI: Key Performance Indicator
AI: Artificial Intelligence	LSTM: Long-Short Term Memory
API: Application Programming Interface	MAE: Mean Absolute Error
AWS: Amazon Web Service	ML: Machine Learning
BMS: Battery Management System	NAR: Nonlinear AutoRegressive
CB: Cell Balancing	OWL: Web Ontology Language
DRL: Deep Reinforcement Learning	RNN: Recurrent Neural Networks
DoS: Denial of Service	SDN: Software-Defined Networking
DDoS: Distributed DoS	Seq2Seq: Sequence-to-Sequence
DNN: Deep Neural Network	SIL: Software-in-the-loop
EV: Electric Vehicle	SoA: State of the Art
GAN: Generative Adversarial Network	SOA: Safe Operation Area
GCP: Google Cloud Platform	SoH: State of Health
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation	SoC: State of Charge
HAL: Hardware abstraction Layer	SoX: State of Health or Charge of other
HIL: Hardware-in-the-loop	SWRL: Semantic Web Rule Language
IoT: Internet of Things	RUL: Remaining Useful Life
KMS: Key Management Service	XAI: eXplainable Artificial Intelligence

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.1 – Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication Activities establishes the basis for the development of a common dissemination & communication plan in the project. This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in ENERGETIC project, designated as “public” regarding the dissemination level. This deliverable is linked with the task T7.1. Updates at M18 and M39. The deliverable will keep updated the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies of the project as well as identifies in detail stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, KPI’s and procedures agreed. This deliverable is alive and will be modified according to the project needs. The results of the strategies implemented will be complementary made visible every year through deliverables D7.5 Exploitation Roadmap (M37).

2. Summary of ENERGETIC project

ENERGETIC is a project funded by the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Commission which goal is to develop the next generation BMS for optimizing batteries’ systems utilisation in the first (transport) and the second life (stationary) in a path towards more reliable, powerful, and safer operations. ENERGETIC project contributes to the field of translational enhanced sensing technologies, exploiting multiple Artificial Intelligence models, supported by Edge and Cloud computing. ENERGETIC’s vision not only encompasses monitoring and prognosis the remaining useful life of a Li-ion battery with a digital twin, but also encompasses diagnosis by scrutinising the reasons for degradation through investigating the explainable AI models.

This involves development of new technologies of sensing, combination and validation of Multiphysics and data driven models, information fusion through Artificial Intelligence, Real time testing and smart Digital Twin development. Based on a solid and interdisciplinary consortium of partners, the ENERGETIC R&D project develops innovative physics and data-based approaches both at the software and hardware levels to ensure an optimised and safe utilisation of the battery system during all modes of operation.

The project's objectives encompass a comprehensive approach to revolutionize battery management. This involves integrating cost-effective sensors into the Battery Management System (BMS), supplying enriched physical data like temperature and ultrasonic details for optimized battery use. A scalable Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL) platform is designed to gather, synchronize, and standardize sensor data for comparison with simulation results, enhancing understanding of battery aging.

Multiphysics modelling tools will analyse State of Charge (SoX) and Remaining Useful Life (RUL) across battery chemistries, while AI models will predict SoX through sensor fusion, utilizing neural networks and explainable AI for fault diagnosis. An innovative Digital Twin (DT) based BMS, incorporating Edge and Cloud computing, aims to monitor batteries more intelligently. The project will also set standards for predictive maintenance in Cloud-based energy storage, fostering future services. Finally, the innovative smart DT-based BMS will be validated experimentally under various usage scenarios, with efforts to disseminate and exploit project outcomes to elevate the technology's impact and readiness.

3. Objectives and Approach of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Communication and Dissemination is an important part of the Horizon Europe projects that all partners must take part in. Communicating European projects should aim at how research and innovation are contributing to an “Innovation Union”.

The main objectives of Communication and Dissemination strategy is to increase the visibility and support the impact of ENERGETIC and its results; Design, manage and deliver the communication and dissemination of the project; Maximize the project’s results by disseminating and communicating updates and the acquired knowledge to relevant identified stakeholders and in terms that are readily understandable to stakeholders in industry, research and academia, policymakers and wider public in order to accelerate the implementation of the research findings. This plan is divided

into 2 complementary activities: Dissemination and Communication (led by Zabala Innovation) and Exploitation (led by Capgemini).

The aim of the **ENERGETIC Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication** is to promulgate findings and innovation developments to key stakeholders to create value within the target communities and initiatives in the EU. What is more, Dissemination and Communication concerns the whole timeline of the project because it is a way of raising awareness for the achievements targeted to the external audience, the scientific community and the potential business users of the products and services developed. It is important to highlight that the organizations engaged in the project, either directly or indirectly, possess a strong and indisputable position and capability to shape and incorporate internal dissemination strategies. This involves engaging additional research, communication, marketing, and business units to amplify the project's influence and effectiveness.

The consortium will ensure that the dissemination materials prepared for the promotion of the research results and benefits do not compromise the interests of the industrial stakeholders prior to disclosure. In this matter, the dissemination approach will be designed and tailored according to the nature of each partner. The findings from the ENERGETIC project will also be tailored to the specific audiences and provide a basis to fostering public support for the development of sustainable, environmentally friendly, and healthy technologies. All aimed to help boost the impact of R&I actions.

The ENERGETIC project is conceived to develop the next generation BMS for optimising batteries' systems utilisation in the first and the second life. The core of the project lies in combining machine learning models with Multiphysics expert models and safety, using Edge or Cloud computing when needed, and even leading path to future services based on data provided through the Cloud. Ultimately, the ENERGETIC project stands poised to usher in a new era of battery management, harnessing the synergy of machine learning, Multiphysics expertise, safety considerations, and adaptable computing solutions, while paving the way for innovative Cloud-driven services yet to come.

3.1. Target Audience and Description

The identification of target audiences of ENERGETIC project is crucial to customise the messages in dissemination and communication activities to every different group. Each group of stakeholders have different points of interest and demands regarding the project.

Dissemination and Communication channels and activities described on this Plan will be clearly focused on them and the messages will be adapted.

The following audience and stakeholders of the sector have been identified before the start of the project and they will be considered at the European, national, and regional level. During its development, partners will be asked to replicate the messages and provide news within their networks.

Target Groups	Communication Channels Aim
TG1: Cell components, BMS and electronic providers	Channels: Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals, specialised conferences; Industry events (market fairs); dedicated workshops; specialised communication channels. Aim: Project involvement and commercial exploitation.
TG2: Sensors, cell & battery manufacturers	Channels: Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals, specialised conferences; Industry events (market fairs); dedicated workshops; specialised communication channels. Aim: Project involvement and commercial exploitation.
TG3: Providers/developers of digital, AI and Cloud computing	Channels: Market and sector fairs, industry Workshops. Aim: Project involvement and commercial exploitation.

TG4: Recyclers and recycling companies	Channels: Website, newsletter, and Social Media; Scientific journals; Circular economy conferences. Aim: Project involvement; Promotion of recycling potential of batteries.
TG5: Technology communities	Channels: Web and social media; Scientific journals, conferences, dedicated workshops. Aim: Project involvement, R&D cooperation, establishment of commercial networks.
TG6: Governments, regulation and standardisation bodies	Channels: Web and social media; Policy Workshops in Brussels; Specialised communication channels (EU Community, etc.). Aim: Project involvement; Policy dissemination.
TG7: Academia and research community	Channels: Web and social media; Scientific journals, conferences. Aim: R&D cooperation.
TG8: End users: EVs and mobility, including aeronautics, and stationary applications	Channels: Website, and social media; Videos; Short presentations for City Interest Groups; Specialized communication channels (EU Community). Open battery conferences Aim: Familiarize public servants with ENERGETIC concepts. Facilitate skill acquisition, implications and benefits of the use of sodium for stationary applications.
TG9: Media outlet, specialised magazines and freelance journalists	Channels: Web and social media; Press releases. Aim: General awareness.
TG10: Citizens and civil society	Channels: Website (dedicated section); Newsletter and social media; Videos; Press releases, articles, press conferences and specific events in pilot sites. Aim: Influencers. Raise awareness on public opinion.
TG11: Student community and bodies from school level to university	Channels: Web and social media; Training sessions; Student internships; Doctorate projects Aim: Promote scientific and technological vocations and formation of high-level scientists and engineers.

Table 1 Target groups

Depending on the specific target audiences, the project will implement different strategies:

- **Stakeholders' engagement:** Industrial stakeholders could be a direct beneficiary of the project and potentially invest in the technology developed, especially to follow-on work with bioengineered natural-source derived nanovesicles. Our industrial stakeholders will ensure that research outcomes can be aligned with their industrial vision for the development of new generation products. We will reach stakeholders through the social media channels and executing social media campaigns in a way to get their attention. Not only social media will ensure that, because our participation in key events will also be a great platform to introduce the project into the ENERGETIC possible community hub.
- **Dissemination:** This includes a stakeholders' engagement and capacity building aims at targeting more experienced audiences (mainly technical and professional audiences, investors, academia etc.) with a focus on transferring technical/technological results through peer-to-peer communication (Legal reference Grant Agreement Article 29) Dissemination will be intensified at the same time that the project advances.
- **Communication:** It aims at lay audiences, end users and house owners, citizens, and the general public (not always closely related with technological issues of ENERGETIC). The communication process covers the whole project (including results), starts at the outset of the project focused on multiple audiences and have a multiplier effect (beyond the project's own community, including the Media and public). ENERGETIC must inform and engage the society, to show how it can benefit their progress. (Legal reference Grant Agreement Article 38.1). The Communication strategy has been launched since the beginning of the project building the ENERGETIC's brand.

3.2. Key Dissemination and Communication Channels and Activities

ACTIONS	DESCRIPTION
Digital Marketing Strategy	
Project website and positioning	An advanced website, providing information about the project and the results, showcasing project's news and acting as a communication channel with the stakeholders and the project media hub.
Social Media Channels	Twitter account - information, general domain news and communicating directly with parties, influencers and key actors; LinkedIn community group to gather all interested stakeholders.
Videos & Multimedia	1 video presenting the project profile and general concept; 1 video presenting the project results and their application; Information pills with focused messages highlighting success stories.
Logo and presentations	HQ professional logo, visual guide, and professional presentation templates (Word for deliverables, power point, press releases, etc. for all partners).
Supporting Communication Material	Posters/Banners/Rollups which will present the project's concept; Flyers/Leaflets that will contain general project information, best practices and ad-hoc information for events.
Press releases	Due to the socioeconomic value of the project, it will catch interest from the Media. Work will be carried out with specialised journalist associations, taking full advantage of the public opinion and their capacity to influence upon the rest of the targeted audiences.
Innovation factsheets	Brief presentation of selected technologies for scale-up, replication and adaptation to other contexts.
Joint events, workshops, round tables & networking with other projects	Events organised/co-organised by project inviting experts, researchers, clients and industry audience. Events where project will be invited to present its work and vision. All events will have presence on the website and the most important will be communicated via Twitter.
Interaction with other EU projects	Participation in EU Cluster initiatives and Networks and Interaction with other cluster initiatives potentially relevant for the project - such as those related to renewable energies and upscaling engineering, will also be promoted

Table 2 Diss&Comm Activities

ZABALA Innovation Consulting is the leader of the WP7 focus on the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities. The actions and processes will be coordinated with the **INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES** (the coordinator of the project), **and the rest of the members of the consortium through the Communication Team, conformed by one member of each partner and the support of the Communication/Marketing/Business Departments of every organization.** It is indispensable a collaboration between the partners to elaborate a meaningful communication strategy that reaches every local, regional, or European sector. To make this happen and reach our objective audience every pill of information should be translated into the local languages the partner of the consortium speaks: French, Estonian, Serbian, German. Every piece of information is going to be written in English.

ZABALA will nominate a person as the Communication Manager of ENERGETIC to coordinate the interaction among the partners, implement and monitor the strategy and act as the main contact of reference for Media and journalists.

Additionally, some specific procedures will be designed to organise in an effective way the external communication, the generation of content on the website, the Social Media work, the review of communication and dissemination materials, and the information and reporting about the participation in events.

All the materials produced to this end by the partners will be reviewed previously its local distribution.

The following table summarizes the main strategies that will be implemented per each typology of organisation:

PARTNERS to be completed	DISSEMINATION TARGET
Large Industry	Great capacities to impact in ESS sector and complementary industry-sectors including their client networks and commercialization channels. Dissemination will focus on identifying and engaging potential customers interested in product/services generated.
SMEs:	Attract new clients and reinforce the loyalty of customer portfolio thanks to the new competitive advantages acquired in terms of boosting current products/services with new solutions. SMEs make available to ENERGETIC their existing client/supplier networks as well as the involvement of their marketing & communication departments.
Academia:	Engage the scientific and industrial communities across Europe to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation. Generate new research lines and training programs aligned with the key pillars of the excellence in science established in HORIZON EUROPE. Involvement of research groups and communication departments in dissemination activities.

Table 3 Partners Strengths

3.2.1. Dissemination and Communication Policy and Rules and Support of the EU

Communication and Dissemination activities are under the rules established in the article 17 of the Horizon's Europe Grant Agreement.

The support to the ENERGETIC project by the European Commission must be recognised in all the dissemination and **communication tools and materials including the following disclaimer:**

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Dissemination activities in ENERGETIC project are deeply wedded with the intellectual property (IP) rights protection, which is clearly stated in **EC-GA Articles 23a**. Practical application of IP rights protection agreed among ENERGETIC project partners.

The main aspects of **IP rights protection** are the following:

- Common agreement on publication of other partners' confidential information or any other information subjected to their IP rights.
- Setting up the dissemination rules and procedures to avoid any potential breach of any partner's IP rights, especially rules and procedures for ENERGETIC project results publications. Understanding the difference between the interests of academia and industry partners of ENERGETIC project. The academia partners tend

to publish all information they have at disposal, which is caused by academia common motivation systems while the industrial partners' decision whether, when and where to publish depends on commercial considerations.

- The basic regulation of the dissemination activities in the CA states that: Dissemination activities including but not restricted to publications and presentations shall be governed by the procedure of **Article 29.1 of the GA** subject to the following provisions.
- “A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — **at least 45 days**, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.
- Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — **30 days** of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.”
- For the avoidance of doubt, no Signatory Party shall have the right to publish or allow the publishing of any data which includes Foreground, Background or Confidential Information of another Signatory Party, even if such data is amalgamated with the Signatory Party's Foreground, or other information, document, or material without the other Signatory Party's prior written approval. Where publications relate to jointly developed results, each Signatory Party involved must be asked for its consent to publish and such consent not to be unreasonably withheld, delayed or conditioned. All draft articles must be sent to the PC, the IM and to the DCM before publication or production for reporting and archiving purposes. This will allow checking if they fulfil the dissemination requirements or whether they conflict with other existing papers. Moreover, the Scientific Board will decide whether it is appropriate to make the document accessible on the Project website or Open Data Repository.

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Furthermore, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must specifically refer to the support of the EC:

For more information, please refer to **article 29 of the Grant Agreement**, which includes these and other considerations regarding the dissemination of the project and the **Open Access**.

All the beneficiaries of the project are committed to follow the guidelines about the use of the EU emblem using it in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes.

Scientific and research publications must include this paragraph:

“The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”.

ENERGETIC project partners will have to provide open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results according to Article 29.2. of the Grant Agreement and [HORIZON EUROPE Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications \(European Commission, 2017\)](#).

3.2.2. Website

The ENERGETIC's website ([Energetic – develop the next generation BMS for optimizing batteries' systems \(energeticproject.eu\)](#)) is the main Media Hub of the project.

ZABALA will update the ENERGETIC website regularly with news and events. Members of the consortium will be requested to promote press releases, offer information to create posts on the website, and other content and materials through their own communication tools and channels: website, Social Media profiles, newsletters, etc.).

Work package leaders are also required to keep informed ZABALA about the developments within these advances. This is a crucial request to follow during the whole implementation of the project because it helps the dissemination of results.

3.2.3. Social Media Guidelines

ZABALA is responsible for the management of the **Twitter and LinkedIn** channels for ENERGETIC project and partners must collaborate by mentioning the ENERGETIC Twitter account, retweeting the messages about the project, and sharing publications on LinkedIn. The Social Media guidelines will gather some pieces of advice and procedures about the participation of the partners in events and the promotion of their visibility on the Social Media channels.

Horizon Europe Programme has published a [Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#) with recommendations.

3.2.4. Communication Materials

ZABALA will develop communication materials (Communication Materials Package following the Guidelines) to promote the ENERGETIC project and will be previously reviewed by the Communication Team. Partners must inform with enough time in advance if they need some of these materials for the participation to events or other requirements. Each partner is responsible in the creation of scientific and research publications/communications devoted to dissemination (previously reviewed by the rest of the partners).

3.2.5. Reporting Events

Partners of the consortium will attend relevant events, conferences, workshops and fairs of the sector. They should be actively involved seeking opportunities to present and showcase the project in their own countries and at both local and European levels. The participation in events must be previously communicated to ZABALA (in order to make visible activities through communication channels), and after the event every partner must complete the events questionnaire with the reporting about the dissemination activity: sum-up, number of attendees, pictures, publications, presentations, press clipping, etc.

3.3. ENERGETIC Visual Guidelines

The first communication action developed after the starting of the project was to create a recognisable brand of ENERGETIC reflecting the main goals of the initiative and offering to the audience/stakeholders a clear identification of the values and messages.

3.3.1. Name

ENERGETIC is the branding name of the project which means: NEXT GENERATION BATTERY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM BASED ON DATA RICH DIGITAL TWIN. The full title should be included in brackets when it is firstly mentioned in a document, then it will be used its abbreviation/acronym.

The project acronym **ENERGETIC must be written in uppercase font.**

3.3.2. Logo and Visual Guidelines

The brand proposal for ENERGETIC is energy and therefore the strokes are expressed in diagonal and vertical lines. The joints are rounded to create harmony between the letters and show absence of aggressiveness, since ENERGETIC is a R&D project that searches welfare and progress for Europe.

The battery is represented by the “+” and “-” symbols, this graphic resource will be displayed throughout the comprehensive visual universe of the brand.

The logo is bounded by a rectangular frame that symbolizes indoor spaces. The technology developed in this project is not only aimed to renewable energy industry, it is also intended for use in homes, so we want to express closeness, proximity and comfort.

To sum up briefly, ENERGETIC logo searches to be a modern, positive and versatile image that embodies the brand's attributes. Communication Tools and Actions

Figure 1 Brand Logo

Figure 2 Reduced version of logo

Figure 3 ENERGETIC colours

4. Communication tools and actions

4.1. Digital Marketing Strategy

With the main aim of attracting and establishing an ENERGETIC community around our general public, the Digital Marketing Strategy has been established with three main pillars:

- **ENERGETIC** website **www.ENERGETICproject.eu** that will be frequently updated through the section of news and events.
- **Social Media and newsletters** to share the advances about the project included on the website and attract visitors and users. This will also be used as a tool to interact and listen to the comments of the stakeholders of the project.
- **SEO** using techniques to obtain a good positioning of the website on Google.

4.1.1. Website

The ENERGETIC website (<https://energeticproject.eu/>) is the main Dissemination and Communication online tool of the project, which will reflect news, advances, and results of the investigation of this project, and the rest of communication actions and the exploitation of the results. Therefore, its design, management, maintenance, and generation of content are key activities. It will showcase the content of sections and defines the expected impacts for the project consortium and the final aim of the investigation of this project.

The website of ENERGETIC is an informative page and a Media Hub for all the public interested in the subject of the project. According to this strategy, messages will be shaped and delivered in an effective manner using Digital Marketing strategies: SEO, creation of content and Social Media channels will be the three pillars to achieve the best results.

The platform will be created to serve as a project content management system. With this aim, the website provides the following content, following guidelines and recommendations of the EC:

- General information about the project.
- Description of all the organizations members of the consortium involved in ENERGETIC.
- Information, objectives, and work packages.
- Calendar of events organized within the framework of the project.
- Press releases and other materials/resources focused on the Media.
- Information about the results as public deliverables and Scientific Papers.
- Latest news.
- Addressing and contact information.
- Appropriate acknowledgment and reference to the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme and disclaimer excluding European Commission responsibility.

The ENERGETIC website has been created with specific objectives, which respond to the communication and dissemination needs of the project. Amongst them, the most highlighted are the following:

- Maintaining a **dynamic website**, all kind of contents will be periodically updated. The website will count with technical articles, investigation papers, public deliverables, pieces of news and policies of the sector, initiatives related to the European Commission, events created by this project or other projects with the same objective, workshops, etc. With this methodology it will improve positioning in Google searchers, and while sharing the content through social networks and the newsletter, more visitors will be attracted to the website.
- The ENERGETIC website is one of the **main communications and dissemination tools** of the project. To maximize the scope of the project, different strategies of digital marketing will be established.

- **SEO** – (Search Engine Optimization): the traffic of visits to the ENERGETIC website will increase progressively throughout the course of the project thanks to the implementation of strategies oriented to organic traffic, always considering the keywords identified for it. ENERGETIC website will be SEO friendly and responds to the following standards.
- **Social networks**: the information hosted in the ENERGETIC website, will be used in the social media channels in a way to increase visits and attract newcomers to the project.
- **Link building**: It will be able to create synergies between the ENERGETIC website and the partners' websites, as well as with other relevant agents of the sector, Horizon Europe projects in the same field encouraging the exchange of links. Instruction to the rest of the partners will be offered with this aim. **See this as an example:** www.zabala.eu/en/projects/ENERGETIC

This is the list of the partner's websites:

- **INSA Strasbourg** (Institut National des Sciences Appliquées, Strasbourg): <https://www.insa-strasbourg.fr/fr/>
 - **CAPGEMINI** (altran prototypes automobiles): <https://www.capgemini.com/fr-fr/secteurs/automobile/>
 - **SnT** (universite du Luxembourg): <https://www.uni.lu/fr/>
 - **EDF** (Electricité De France) : <https://www.edf.fr/en>
 - **HKA Hochschule karlsruhe**: <https://www.h-ka.de/>
 - **THIL** (tajfun hil drustvo sa ogranicenom odgovornoscu za istrazivanje): <https://tajfun-hil.ls.rs/>
 - **TalTech** (Tallinna Tehnikaülikool): <https://taltech.ee/>
 - **POWERUP**: <https://powerup-technology.com/about-us/>
 - **FORSEE POWER**: <https://www.forseepower.com/>
 - **BATH University**: <https://www.bath.ac.uk/>
 - **ZABALA Innovation**: <https://www.zabala.fr/>
 - **FEMTO-ST** (Université de Technologie de Belfort – Montbéliard): <https://www.femto-st.fr/fr>
 - **COVENTRY UNIVERSITY**: <https://www.coventry.ac.uk/>
- **Responsive Web Design** makes ENERGETIC page look good on all devices (desktops, tablets, and phones). The incorporation of the state-of-the-art techniques in design also create a quick and intuitive user experience browsing the web.

ENERGETIC website will be SEO friendly and responds to the following standards:

Keyword optimisation: the content of the website will have several keywords inserted regularly on the text and design modules, which will help us generate traffic through search. Some of the keywords proposed are:

- Battery Management Systems
- Digital Twins
- Energy transition
- Resource efficiency
- Battery Sensors
- Innovation
- Flexibility
- Validation case
- Data driven models
- Public Energy
- Energy consumers
- Energy prosumers
- AI models
- Multiphysics Models
- Cloud and Edge Computing

- **Content feed**: to avoid being penalized by search engines, it is important to be constant and publish regularly. A good option to keep the website active is by the promotion of it in the rest of our channels, thus building links to the content. Google will then recognize it as a relevant and interesting.

- **Content Organization:** The content is organized in a logical way and considering the European guidelines of best practices. This is not only good for SEO; it also helps visitors to find other related content easily.
- **Content Promotion:** Increase visibility to new content by sharing it on social networks and building links to the content (both internally and from external sites).

The website has a legal warning and a policy politic that promises the fulfilment of the GDPR.

Figure 4 Screenshot website: energeticproject.eu

4.1.2. Social Media Channels

The creation of a “ENERGETIC community” will increase the visibility and impact of the results attained in the project. In fact, viral marketing strategies linked with the website and its new content periodically created will be implemented based on Twitter (@ENERGETICEU), and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/energeticproject/>) Social Media tools.

The Social Media accounts are already set and updated regularly. ZABALA leads this task with the support of all partners communication departments to facilitate the reach out to wide media and promote interaction and lines of conversation on the Social Media channels.

ZABALA will lead this task that will require inputs and support for dissemination by all partners. Recommendations and requirements of the [Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects of the HORIZON EUROPE Programme](#) will be followed.

4.1.2.1. Twitter: <https://twitter.com/EnergeticEU>

People use Twitter to find out what is going on in the world right now, instantly sharing information and connecting with people and businesses across the globe. It offers a great opportunity for ENERGETIC to reach an international audience of current and potential stakeholders.

ENERGETIC is using Twitter to establish meaningful connections with an active and relevant audience (EC, policy makers, stakeholders of the industry, local authorities, and general public). These connections can produce beneficial opportunities for the project across the network of stakeholders. It will serve as well to tell everybody in real time what is happening in the co-creation workshops and other activities of the project.

Figure 5 twitter Screenshot

The credentials for Twitter are the following:

- @ENERGETICEU – twitter handle
- #ENERGETIC – hashtag

To maximize the impact of the project on Social Media Channels, images and gifs will be crated and shared with all the partners.

Tweets can be directed to specific accounts using @TWITTER-HANDLE in tweets.

This is the list of the project partners' Twitter handles or hashtags (in case they have not Twitter account)-They will be mentioned in the ENERGETIC Twitter account to generate conversations and interactions always is possible:

#ENERGETIC	#Data	#BMS	#HorizonEurope
#Energetic	#BatteryManagementSystem	#AI	#EnergyTransition
#ENERGETIC_EU	#DigitalTwins	#EUProjects	#Sustainability
#Energy	#PublicDataSpace	#Innovation	#ResourceEfficiency
#EnergyCommunities	#BatterySensors	#Multiphysics	#Flexibility
#RenewableEnergy	#AIModels	#EUFunding	#CloudComputing
#PublicEnergy	#EnergyConsumers	#Transport	#EdgeComputing

Table 4 hashtags

4.1.2.2. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/99880742/admin/feed/posts/>

LinkedIn is currently the main business network in the world. Stakeholders, which ENERGETIC needs to connect with, are in LinkedIn, so it is appropriate to implement some actions.

A LinkedIn company page will establish ENERGETIC public image on a global scale as a reputable and trustworthy project. Although many people view the Social Media site LinkedIn only as a site for job hunters and for growing professional network, LinkedIn is an equally effective tool for nurturing referral relationships.

By producing content that our viewers want to see about the project and share with others, our viewers become engaged advocates of ENERGETIC and can expand our global influence.

ENERGETIC should post as many status updates as our content supports. We will reach more of our audience and extend our reach as we post more often. The ENERGETIC LinkedIn profile is a supplement to the website, helps driving traffic to the site and offers a way out to promote the project.

Figure 6 ENERGETIC's LinkedIn screenshot

4.1.2.3. YOUTUBE: ENERGETIC EU

Youtube channel will serve to share ENERGETIC promotional videos and recoding of the trainings. The main objective will be to complement the influence of Twitter and LinkedIn, by the feedback across the platforms. Multimedia content (videos in particular), create deeper engagement rates in visitors, thus strengthening the dissemination and communication strategy.

4.2. Communication Materials Package

To effectively broadcast the messages of the project in events and promote the project on the Social Media channels, different communication materials have been foreseen, following the visual guidelines applied for the logo and the website.

- **ENERGETIC presentation (Powerpoint)** in English including of the project's description, objectives and expected results will be prepared. It will be completed and validated by the partners of the consortium.
- **ENERGETIC roll-up** will contain the main information to be used in events and conferences along the whole project timeline.
- **ENERGETIC brochure & flyers** will also be produced. Similarly, they will contain the project's most important information to be versatile for all kinds of events. If necessary, targeted flyers can be produced for key events.

4.3. Media Relations

The Media and journalists are key agents to transmit information about the project to other stakeholders and the general public. They have a lot of influence and may have a positive impact to increase results, raise awareness and offer information to the rest of the society about the ENERGETIC project. Relationships with Media will be established through the Press Office of ENERGETIC, led by ZABALA and the collaboration of the rest of the partners.

This task will be accomplished at European, national, and regional levels on the following way:

- ZABALA will prepare the press releases regarding the ENERGETIC milestones and other detected opportunities to communicate in English and Spanish.
- Once the press release is approved by the Communication Team, every partner will translate the press release into the local language and will send it to their contacts through its Communication Department.
- The press release will be included on their own websites and shared in their Social Media channels.
- Impacts will be monitored and included in the press-clipping (visible in the ENERGETIC website) and in the Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities

To make the most of our content, we will need to make sure we are distributing it correctly. Content promotion through some distribution platforms will allow us to win audiences and optimize our news and information.

The **Horizon Europe results platform** will use as well to distribute news releases and posts generated for the website.

4.4. Events

The events are one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow to connect with industrial stakeholders, and the research community, encouraging networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also feed of content the communication channels and tools (website, social media, press releases) generating great impacts on different audiences.

The strategy of participation of events will be set up at three different levels:

- By the side of each partner participating in the usual events of the sector.
- Joining presentations of the project in previously selected events organized by the EC and other key institutions/organizations.
- Events organized and promoted by ENERGETIC collaborating with other initiatives and organizations to generate synergies.

4.4.1. Presence at Key Events

The project's results will be communicated and disseminated at the relevant European events/trade fairs to present their main added value to a potential client/end-user portfolio. This participation could include the development of pilot demonstrations, show cases and presentations. Moreover, **the project's partners will take part of strategic workshops involving an International Advisory Board (IAB)**, to discuss about the best way to introduce the results in different countries with key stakeholders. Synergies with other Horizon Europe battery projects will be explored in order to establish collaboration areas and foster the organization of joint initiatives. Also, with associations like the following ones:

The following list is an example list of the kind of events that will be in the radar of ENERGETIC for communication and dissemination activities:

4.4.1.1. Project Events:

- Training seminars (1 at M24 online and 1 at M39 face-to-face during final event);
- 3 stakeholders' workshops (1 at M12, 1 at M24 online and the last one at M39 during final event);
- 1 intermediary and 1 final event

4.4.1.2. EU Events, Trade Fairs, Projects & Workshops

- Advanced Battery Power 2023 & 2025, EUROBAT General Assembly and Forum 2024,
- Hanover Fair 2025 or 2026, Battery Show Europe annually from 2023 and onwards, Automotive Testing Expo
- Europe annually from 2023 and onwards
- Battery Show North America 2023 is the largest battery industry event in North America, bringing together the entire battery value chain under one roof. The show will take place in Novi, Michigan, every year.
- Battery Show North America 2023 is the largest battery industry event in North America, bringing together the entire battery value chain under one roof. The show will take place in Novi, Michigan, 2024-2025.
- Automotive World Congress & Exposition is a global event that brings together the automotive industry, including suppliers, manufacturers, dealers, and policymakers. The show will take place in Detroit, Michigan.
- Automotive World Congress & Exposition is a global event that brings together the automotive industry, including suppliers, manufacturers, dealers, and policymakers. The show will take place in Detroit, Michigan.
- Intersolar Europe is a leading international exhibition for the solar industry, covering the entire value chain from modules and components to systems and solutions. The show will take place in Munich, Germany.

4.4.1.3. Scientific Conferences Targeted

- Battery Experts Forum (Frankfurt) annually.
- Advanced Automotive Battery Conference (AABC) annually.
- IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference & Expo (ITEC)
- IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)
- IEEE Conference on Control Technology and Applications (CCTA)
- International Conference on Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems
- IEEE International Symposium on Diagnostics for Electrical Machines
- Power Electronics and Drives
- IEEE Intelligent Vehicle Symposium (IV)
- IEEE Conference on Vehicle Power and Propulsion
- International Conference on Battery Management and Intelligent Batteries ICBMIB
- International Conference on Battery Management Systems for Future Electric Vehicles ICBMSFEV
- International Conference on Batteries and Battery Management Systems ICBBMS,
- International Conference on Mobile Edge Computing and Applications ICMECA,
- International Conference on Security and Privacy of Connected Vehicular Cloud Computing ICSPCVC,
- International Conference on Green Cloud Computing Systems and Technologies ICGCCST,
- Battery Show Europe

4.4.1.4. European Policies, clustering with EU initiatives and positioning of the consortium

The project also will provide inputs for to contribute on the policies and initiatives of the sector:

- 3 workshops for policy makers. At least 2 events during and at the final of the project involving.
- the key agents of the EP (ITRE, ENVI, STOA committees) EC (DG Energy), EIT InnoEnergy,
- Technological Platforms as ETIP Batteries, ETIP- SNET and BRIDGE initiative etc.

The participation of partners in events will be made visible through the ENERGETIC website and Social Media channels contributing to increase the community of stakeholders and public interested in the project. General and technical presentations of ENERGETIC will be showcased in a face-to-face interaction with the stakeholders.

This table will be periodically updated, and inputs will be compiled.

KPI's: 3 workshops for policy makers. At least 2 events during and at the final of the project involving the key agents of the EP (ITRE, ENVI, STOA committees) EC (DG Energy), EIT InnoEnergy, Technological Platforms as ETIP Batteries, ETIP-SNET and BRIDGE initiative etc.

Industry: Average of 2 event a year. **Academia:** Average of 1 event a year. / **Beyond ENERGETIC (3 years):** participation in 3 scientific conferences and publication of 2 papers a year

4.5. Webinars

To promote collaboration, knowledge sharing, and innovation, we are planning to host a series of webinars throughout the project's duration.

4.5.1. Our Webinar Approach:

The webinars will be organised with a frequency of at least two per year. The main aim is to try to stimulate in-depth discussions, insights, and case studies on Smart Batteries, BMS, and cloud integration. To provide a comprehensive and wider view, a wide range of experts, such as industry experts, renowned researchers, and representatives from leading companies, will be involved to give a diverse perspective.

In addition, to make the activity even more interactive, it is foreseen that there will be a Q&A moment at the end of each webinar in which the participants will have the possibility to interact directly with the experts involved.

The main objective of the webinars is to give participants the possibility to stay at the forefront of advancements in Smart Batteries and BMS technology while networking with industry leaders, researchers, and innovators. Moreover, the webinars will provide insights into real-world applications and case studies, while each participant will contribute to discussions shaping the future of battery technology.

4.5.2. Webinar Topics:

Our aim is to foster a dynamic community of professionals, researchers, and industry leaders dedicated to advancing Smart Batteries and BMS technology.

Five are the main topics that will be addressed during the webinars:

- Introduction to Smart Batteries and BMS - Exploring the fundamentals.
- Cloud Integration for Battery Management - Leveraging cloud technology.
- Case Studies and Best Practices - Real-world applications.
- Sustainability and Green Energy Storage - Environmentally conscious solutions.
- Emerging Trends and Innovations - What's on the horizon.

4.6. Scientific Publications

It is expected that ENERGETIC project develops a significant amount of research results which will be disseminated to different key scientific communities. Thus, RTD/Academia Partners will dedicate strong efforts in publishing scientific papers under the framework of global recognized scientific conferences and journals that count on high impact index.

Each paper must be submitted to **revision and validation of the publication** 45 days **in advance to the consortium members**. The publications will be made freely and openly available via online repository like ZENODO, one of the repositories approved by the EC.

ENERGETIC project partners will have to **provide Open Access** to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

Each ENERGETIC project partner will ensure **Open Access** (via the repository) to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata will be in a standard format and will include all items as it is indicated in the Article 29.2. of the Grant Agreement.

The ENERGETIC website www.energetic.eu will include articles summarizing the scientific publications in a divulged way and will be submitted to CORDIS Wire

International Reference Journals:

- Advanced Energy Materials, Joule
- ACS Macro letters
- Journal of Power Sources
- IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification
- IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics
- IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion
- IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications
- MDPI Battery
- MDPI Vehicles

KPI's Industry: Average of 1 conference publication/year. **Academia:** At least 3 conferences/publications a year. / **Beyond ENERGETIC** (3 years): participation in 3 scientific conferences and publication of 2 papers a year

5. Specific Campaigns (training brochure) / workshops/

5.1. Training Programme

Seminars directed at the scientific and academic community related to the project's innovations and research will be organized to present techniques and protocols developed in the project, as well as the latest project results. The trainings will include webinars, workshops and materials that will be at the disposal of the participants and interested public on the website. The first training event will be held online at M24 while the second will be organized during the ENERGETIC final event.

Zabala will lead the campaign through the ENERGETIC communication channels to promote the trainings as well as the communication materials.

Complementary to the dissemination and communication Strategy Zabala will offer to the members of the consortium specific webinars to create synergies between the members focus on the dissemination and communication plan.

6. KPI's and Monitoring

ZABALA will coordinate the **Plan and Strategy for Dissemination and Communication** of ENERGETIC and its activities with the involvement of all the member of the consortium. Each partner will make use of its communication tools and channels, networks, and collaboration with the goal of reach the stakeholders of the project and build the ENERGETIC

community. The partners must provide all the relevant information and feedback as well to complete the Communication Reports on a regular basis since the start of the project.

ZABALA will compile all the information about the events attended, upcoming events, other networking and collaborative activities, as well as the impacts on Media for the press-clipping and the distribution of the communication materials through a form sent by e-mail. If necessary, partners could receive calls by phone or requested emails.

These will be some of the main indicators we are going to monitor to measure the Return of the Investment (ROI) in communications. Monitoring and analytics will be incorporated on the web and Social Media in ENERGETIC's digital marketing and communication processes, as a source of essential information for monitoring key indicators.

All the impacts will be compiled in the **deliverable 8.5 Report and Dissemination and Communication Activities**.

ACTIONS	KPI's
Project Website (M4)	25,000 visits / Updated with contents. Beyond ENERGETIC (3 years): Keep website project active and updated with contents
Social Media: Promotion of progress, events. Dedicated ENERGETIC social media accounts (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube). Use of partners' existing strong online resources to share findings, thoughts, and related interesting work. (M4)	LinkedIn (>1,300 interactions) Twitter (+300 followers, 800 posts) / Beyond ENERGETIC (3 years): To keep alive the social media accounts created
Communication Toolkit: Corporate design (templates, layouts). Leaflets, brochure, poster, banner, and other materials create a uniform and recognizable brand. All communication materials will include the EC logo and EC funding acknowledgement. (M3)	Communication toolkit will be created after the launch of the website.
Press kit & Releases: A package of information to facilitate press publications: the project's achievements, talking points, blogs and short articles, graphical material and basic description (M3)	4 press releases / Beyond ENERGETIC (3 years): 1 press releases/year, 2 independent journalist article/year and 2 interviews/year
Promotional videos: Professional videos presenting the project, its activities, and its benefits; Thematic videos for wider societal engagement. (M6)	2 videos; ≥400 views per video on YouTube/Twitter; Available >3 years beyond the Project
Innovation factsheets: Brief presentation of selected technologies for scale-up, replication and adaptation to other contexts. (M36)	4 Innovation factsheets; >100 downloads, >80 retweets

Table 5 KPI's Table

7. Horizon Europe Request and Coordination with the EC

According to the EC Grant Agreement participants agree to:

- ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY 17.1 Communication — Dissemination — Promoting the action - Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the Media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner. **Before engaging in a**

communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority.

- **Ensure Open Access** (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

8. Annex

8.1. Visual Guidelines

Figure 7 Front Page

CONTEXT

ENERGETIC project aims to develop the next generation BMS for optimizing batteries' systems utilization in the first (transport) and the second life (stationary) in a path towards more reliable, powerful, and safer operations. ENERGETIC project contributes to the field of translational enhanced sensing technologies, exploiting multiple Artificial Intelligence models, supported by Edge and Cloud computing. ENERGETIC's vision not only encompasses monitoring and prognosis the remaining useful life of a Li-ion battery with a digital twin, but also encompasses diagnosis by scrutinizing the reasons for degradation through investigating the explainable AI models. This involves development of new technologies of sensing, combination and validation of multiphysics and data driven models, information fusion through Artificial Intelligence, Real time testing and smart Digital Twin development. Based on a solid and interdisciplinary consortium of partners, the ENERGETIC R&D project develops innovative physics and data-based approaches both at the software and hardware levels to ensure an optimized and safe utilization of the battery system during all modes of operation.

Figure 8 Context of ENERGETIC

CONCEPT

ENGINEERING
BATTERY
RENEWABLE
ENERGY
TECH

Figure 9 ENERGETIC Brand

Figure 10 Reduced version of the logo

Figure 10 Font of the project

COLOURS

Figure 11 ENERGETIC colour